

TOWARDS BUILDING THE NIGERIA OF OUR DREAM: A NIGER DELTA SECURITY PERSPECTIVE

A Lead Paper Delivered By

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INTRODUCTION

Let me begin by thanking the organizers of this conference for the kind invitation extended to me as the lead paper presenter at the National Sociological conference holding at the University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State. All intellectual fields are profoundly shaped by their social settings. This is particularly true of sociology, which not only is derived from the setting but takes the social setting as its basic matter. The long series of the industrial revolution and political revolutions that were ushered in by the French Revolution in 1789 and carried over through the Nineteenth Century were of the utmost significance in the development of sociology. The impacts of these revolutions on many societies was enormous, and many positive changes resulted. However, what attracted the attention of many early theorists was not the positive consequences, but the negative effects of such changes. These writers were particularly disturbed by the resulting chaos and disorder, especially in France. They were united in a desire to restore order to society. Some of the early thinkers of this period literally, wanted return to the peaceful and relatively orderly days of the middle ages (Ritzer, 2008; Ritzer & Stepnisky, 2014).

The more sophisticated thinkers recognized that social change had made such a return impossible. Consequently, they sought instead to find new bases of order in societies that had been overturned by the political revolutions of the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. This interest in the issue of social order was one of the major concerns of classical sociological theorists, especially Comte, Durkheim, and Parsons. At least as important as political revolution in shaping of sociological theorizing was the Industrial Revolution, which swept through many Western societies, mainly in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. The point needing stress is that the industrial revolution was not a single event but many interrelated developments that culminated in the transformation of the Western world from largely agricultural to overwhelmingly industrial system (Ritzer, 2008; Ritzer & Stepnisky, 2014).

Large number of people left farms and agricultural work for industrial occupations offered in the burgeoning factories. The factories themselves were transformed by a long series of technological improvements. Large economic bureaucracies arose to provide the many services needed by industry and the emerging capitalist system. In this economy, the ideal was a free market place where the many products as of and industrial system could be exchanged. Within this system a few profited greatly while the majority worked long hours for low wages. A reaction against capitalism in general followed and led to the emergence of labour movement as well as to various radical movements aimed at overthrowing the capitalist system (Ritzer, 2008).

The point of fact is that the industrial revolution, capitalism, and the reaction against them all involved enormous upheaval in Western Society, an upheaval that affected Sociologists greatly. Four major figures in the early history of sociological theorizing- Karl Marx, Max Weber, Emile Durkheim and George Simmel-were preoccupied, as were many lesser thinkers, with these changes and the problems they created for society as a whole. They spent their lives studying these problems, and in many cases they endeavoured to develop programmes that would help solve them (Ritzer, 2008).

Partly, as a result of the Industrial Revolution, large numbers of people in the 19th and 20th centuries were uprooted from their rural homes and moved to urban settings. This massive migration was caused in large part, by the jobs created by the industrial system in the urban areas. But it presented many difficulties for those people who had to adjust to urban life. In addition, the expansion of the cities produced a seemingly endless list of urban problems-overcrowding, pollution, noise, traffic, and so forth. The nature of urban life and its problems attracted the attention of many early sociologists, especially Max Weber and George Simmel were preoccupied, as were many lesser thinkers, with these changes, and the problems they created for society as a whole (Ritzer, 2008).

Social changes brought on by political revolution, the Industrial Revolution, and urbanization had a profound effect on religiosity. This is not surprising because many early sociologists came from religious backgrounds and were actively in some cases professionally, involved in religion (Hinkle & Hinkel, 1954). These Sociologists brought to the discipline the same objectives as they had in their religious lives. They wished to improve people's lives (Vidich and Lyman, 1985). For some, such as Comte, sociology was transformed into a religion. For others, their sociological theories bore an unmistakable religious imprints. Durkheim wrote one of his major works on religion. Morality played a key role not only on Durkheim's sociology but also in the work of Talcott Parsons. A large portion of Weber's work also was devoted to the religions of the world. Marx, too had an interest in religiosity, but his orientation was far more critical.

My point of departure is to approach my discussion from security challenges confronting the Nigerian State at a critical juncture of her post-colonial history some of which manifest in ethnic and religious forms, resource wars and competitions to occupy political space in Nigeria's contemporary democratic governance. The Niger Delta comprising of Bayelsa, Rivers and Delta state¹, Imo, Abia, Cross River, Ondo, Akwa Ibom and Edo states is the duck that lays the Nigerian golden egg. The Region generates about 95% of foreign exchange earnings and 80% of all budgetary revenues². Although there are conflicting records of proven and probable oil and gas deposits in the region, 2006 estimates³ ranked Nigeria 1st in Africa and 7th in the world in oil and gas deposits. The region's importance as Nigeria's economic mainstay is expected to rise with the new federal government policy of boosting investments in oil and gas to raise Nigeria's daily oil production and transform the gas sub-sector into a money spinner. The Region is equally strategic in the ongoing power generation projects, proposed

¹ They are described as the core-Niger Delta states as a result of the size of oil and gas found in them

² Democracy, Oil and Politics in the Niger Delta: Linking Citizens' Perceptions and Policy Reform- L. Adele Jinadu etal, 2007, pg. 9

³ About 187 Trillion Cubic Feet, while the NNPC estimates about 600 Trillion cubic feet - Prof. Anthony Adegbuluge, former Presidential Adviser on Energy Matters, at the World Bank Energy Week, in March 2006,

export programme⁴ of the new administration creating an urgent need to address the problems of the Region. The Niger Delta Experience and its Anti-Dotes” becomes memorable because the Region continues to be in the national and international limelight and search light, notably because of the oil and gas resources that sustain the gigantic Nigerian State and associated human tragedies that constitute potent threat to Nigeria’s fledgling democracy and collective security.

Our collective failure to stand and raise alarm and mobilize the citizens to avert the current disaster staring us in the face and salvage the security of this resource endowed region is becoming more disastrous. The seemingly intractable state of insecurity in the Niger Delta is an indication that the State is sitting on a socio-political tinder box or volcano. The situation is attributed to failing formal and informal governance structure which places control of petroleum resources in the hands of government that is unaccountable and loathes the people it is purportedly representing; and public administrative system that denies them the right to benefit from the land on which they live. Poverty is widespread but most prevalent in rural communities where only about 27% have access to safe drinking water and about 30% have access to electricity⁵; many riverine areas have never seen electricity. There is 1 doctor per 82,000 people rising up to 132,000 people in some rural areas. Access to education, considered an essential element for remedying the crisis, is abysmally low in the region. While about 76% of all Nigerian children attend primary school, the figure is a mere 30-40% in the region.

The very low level of industrial development and the attendant unemployment and under-employment in the Region is alarming. Development is also stifled by the absence of basic infrastructure- transportation, telecommunication, electricity, water, skill acquisition centres and vocational schools, social restiveness, conflict and shortage of land for development⁶. The list however represents symptoms of a political process that is disenfranchising and produces a government that is unaccountable and shielded from its constitutional responsibility, credibility deficit of government and public administrators, a long history of institutional weakness and absence of effective checks and balances at federal, state and local government councils, fiscal indiscipline and weak capacity in service delivery agencies and institutions, absence of the rule of law and discredited judicial process that protects the ‘strong’ rich and frustrates the weak poor. They are symptomatic of an underlying tension between an oppressed and frustrated majority that wants to be heard and taken seriously in decisions to manage the collective wealth and an elite class that is power-drunk and rides on the frustrations of the majority to keep them subservient and hold onto power as guarantee for controlling the rent machine.

Since returning to civilian rule in 1999, progress has been slow towards building a social contract where elected representatives act on behalf of and for the welfare of the people. Even when oil prices at record levels and government revenues in excess of \$50 billion per year, poverty rates remain unacceptably high, income inequality rose and most human development indices fell below expectations. With government officially declaring that the country is in recession, the situation is worse than it was over a decade ago. Consequently, levels of

⁴ Proposed gas export projects include the West Africa Gas Pipeline Project; West Africa Power Pool project; LNG Projects- in Brass (Bayelsa) and Olokola (Ogun/Ondo State), Power Projects etc- all of which rely heavily on gas from the Niger Delta.

⁵ This is considered to be below national average

⁶ Niger Delta Regional Development Master Plan, 2006, pg.93

dissatisfaction with the government as well as democratic institutions are dangerously high. The fact that since 2005 the country has confronted two insurgencies—one in the Niger Delta and the other from an Islamic insurrection in the North-East of the country reinforces the fragility of the current situation and the extraordinary risk of Nigeria slipping into civil conflict.

It was after all born amidst the extraordinary political violence of the early 1960s and subsequently the horrors of the Biafra war. Ethnic, religious, electoral and military violence, especially since 1999, have been widespread and endemic (by some estimates over 10,000 mortalities and over 200,000 are internally displaced). Nigeria is conflicted, one might say, but it is not necessarily fragile (Joab-Peterside; Porter and Watts, 2012). As a resource-dependent petro-state⁷, Nigeria figures in policy debates as a textbook case (see Ross 2012; Collier 2007) of the ‘resource curse’, that is to say it is a casualty of a raft of State deficits and dysfunctions (the Dutch Disease, poor fiscal management, authoritarian rule, corruption, “survival of the fittest”, underachievement of HDIs) and relatedly forms of conflict (and civil war) associated with resource predation and looting.

The State pathologies are derived from the existence of, and state dependence on, natural resource rents—supernormal (oligopoly or monopoly) profits – which tend to be the product of enclave, capital intensive industries with limited linkages that accrue to landlords (in the case of oil this is typically the State). The rentier state hinges on the extent to which resources like oil in the Nigerian case provide the fiscal basis of the State (so-called ‘resource-dependency’ rather than ‘resource abundance’) (Dunning 2008). The sort of prescriptions derived from the ‘resource curse’ literature fit uneasily with the Niger Delta because insurgency in the Delta – and the wider field of social conflict – points to complex conflict dynamics where causes and impacts mutate and telescope over time in a way that belies the usual static dichotomies. When viewed through this lens, sliding into permanent levels of conflict would be catastrophic.

I argue that the problem is best characterized as the massive problem of structural condition of Nigeria’s federalism; authoritarian and kleptocratic rule and the prevailing troublesome character of the politics of succession at the Federal and State level. Jinadu underscores this point thus:

The coexistence of two nations, in the form of the juxtaposition of excessive, even criminal wealth in few hands, against a huge population of impoverished Nigerians...militarized physical violence by agencies of the state to cower legitimate and understandable agitational resistance by the victims of structural violence, institutional inequalities, and the existence of historically marginalized groups are pervasive features of our society, aggravated and deepened by the rampaging process of globalization, under the hegemonic drive of triumphalist neoliberalism and its protagonist, which refuses to draw a distinction between production and distribution, and which, as a result, poses a false antithesis or antimony between the State and the individual, and between the State and society(2007:17).

⁷Nigeria possesses the largest oil and natural gas reserves in Africa, and the 14th (7th) largest oil (gas) reserve in the world (Oyefusi 2012). Proven oil and gas reserves stand at 37.2 billion barrels and 184 trillion cubic feet respectively (Nigeria is in this sense gas rich). Roughly two-thirds of production is on-shore, the remainder is derived off-shore in both shallow and deep water, respectively. Oil revenues typically account for 85% of government revenues and almost the entire export portfolio (by value).

The above is why the problem of insecurity in Nigeria is bound up with the character of the State, as one captured by the governing elite to accumulate wealth. This is why we need to approach the problem from a modified structuralist-materialist perspective. Within this context how do we conceptualize security and which perspective best explains the Niger Delta situation. Answer to these questions is the object of the next section.

Dimensions of the Security Challenge

Generally, the security situation is alarming as the nation's current security landscape contains potential threats such as sectarian violence, civil crises, communal clashes, cultism, killings and robberies, vandalism, proliferation of light weapons and small arms and terrorism (Joab-Peterside, 2010, THE WILL, 2012, Political Economist, 2016)). Kidnappings, hitherto restricted to the Niger Delta, have spread to other parts of Nigeria. This crime graduated from mere abductions to its present status. In the early period, the victims were foreigners. Now, the targets are no longer foreigners alone. Practically, every Nigerian (the very old, children as young as three years have been taken hostage) is a potential target. Data from the 2008 global kidnap index by the online Tourism site revealed that Nigeria was placed sixth among the countries with high kidnapping rates. This rating puts Nigeria among countries with kidnapping as serious problem behind the Philippines, Venezuela, Columbia, Brazil, and Mexico. In recent times, the figure may be higher especially in the Niger Delta where hostage taking graduated from an instrument deployed by agitators to draw attention to the nagging problem of underdevelopment to an industry. What is more worrisome is that state security forces appear overwhelmed by the prevailing anarchy (Joab-Peterside, 2013).

Different phases of contentious politics - periods of escalation and resurgence, periods of state repression and violence - coupled with accumulating human insecurity contributed to the deepening disorder and ungovernability of the 2006-2009 period. Ijaw politics figured centrally in the new post-1995 landscape of militancy but many ethnic minorities were drawn into the militant struggle for oil rents on the one side and illicit activities on the other. With the power of hindsight one can see a set of dynamics developing over four decades in which power moved to a younger generation - the politics of youth movements and the demographic bulge are both key – whose social and economic prospects were limited if not truncated. By the 2000s, the anger, resentment and alienation across a wide trans-ethnic social class of alienated and disempowered youth were palpable and profound. A key current in the escalation of violence by ethnic militias is the recruitment of their leaders to secure electoral victory through violence and intimidation. The governing elites who succeeded in capturing the State administer it to the exclusion of those who are disempowered in competition over political power.

Defence of communities from external aggression constitutes a potent security challenge. This is particularly the case in inter-communal struggle over land and associated benefits. Many communities develop collective responses to insecurity as wealthy and politically influential indigenes invest in procurement of arms to fortify their communities against external attacks. It is under this circumstance that most community vigilante groups emerged to perform responsibility which State Security Forces have abdicated. In some states, wealthy residents invested in sophisticated alarms, security guards, and other forms of private policing to protect their families and properties.

Continuation of the urban bias colonial development policy that exploited natural resources from the rural areas for development of urban centers by the State encouraged rural –urban drift as most rural inhabitants especially the youths migrated to the cities in search for better life. Lack of attention and commitment to alleviating the plight of oil communities in terms of provision of basic social amenities, continuous shrinking of physical space that in the past sustained traditional livelihood means such as farming and fishing due to environmental degradation and increased oil production activities accentuated migration of the productive segment of the population to the city. This forced migration put available social infrastructure and social services under severe pressure.

For instance, excruciating housing problem gave rise to springing up of squatter/slum settlements. These settlements lack social amenities, State Security presence in form of Police Stations or Posts that made them safe haven for criminals. Children born in these settlements and those whose parents were compelled to take up residence there took to the streets establishing a sub-culture different from that accepted by the larger society. While the girls embraced prostitution to augment family income, the boys took to crime to earn a living. This is how the slums created pools of vulnerable young men who provided the foundation for urban cults and gangs. Most urban cults and gangs in core Niger Delta States especially Rivers State, originated in the slum settlements from where they spread to communities.

The rising wave of cult gangsterism is frightening as it seems that anomie is the order of the day. For instance, the month of February 2016 virtually on daily basis, criminal gangs and cult groups armed with automatic rifles, knives, bottles and other dangerous weapons engaged in savage fight and unleash mayhem on the citizenry. Cult war took place in Rivers State, where rival gangs were up in arms against one another in brutal fights. The affected council areas are Abua/Odual; Ahoada West and Ogba/Egbema? Ndoni (ONELGA), Khana and Gokana. These fights forced thn State Governor, Nyesom Wike, to ban commercial motorcyclist in affected Local Government councils.

Land and boundary disputes are common in communities but factors which prolong and make such disputes difficult to resolve include vaulting territorial ambition. Land and boundary disputes become more fierce and disturbing where industrial and development projects are sited or proposed to be located in communities that have old standing land and boundary disputes. Expectations of compensations to be paid, opportunities for contracts and employment of local indigenes often escalate long-standing land disputes into major crises. In some cases, access to farm/grassing land had also provoked violent conflicts. Unemployment, especially youth unemployment did not help matter either. Ethnic “armies” and militias drew membership from army of unemployed youths who have lost hope of earning a living through legitimate means. Lack of opportunities through legitimate avenues made most youths believe that violence is the only option left open to them to reverse the decades of neglect and finally gain a small foot hold from which they can help themselves. Search for illegal sectors of social mobility gave rise to fights over control of organized crime such as drug dealing, robberies, car theft, extortion rackets, and petty theft in the State capitals and involvement in criminal activities and organizations.

According to Ogah and Hassan (2012), piracy and armed banditry on the West African maritime domain, particularly Nigeria, assumed a disturbing dimension in recent years with oil vessels as prime targets. In some cases, crew members were either killed or maimed and their

oil cargos drained into other waiting vessels. The social field of violence in the Delta encompassed a number of differing agents, actors and dynamics. A large body of research (Ikelegbe 2006, Ukeje 2011; Langer and Ukoha 2009; Obi and Rustad 2011; Oyefusi 2007, 2012) pointed to the following forms of conflict:

Violent conflicts between oil companies and community youth groups (over compensation, employment, and access to cash payments)

Conflicts between communities and companies over host community status, spill compensation (or ritual/cultural site desecration) and MOUs (Ugborodu, Soku)

Electoral violence and political thuggery (for example, the 2003 elections, and the 2003-4 violence, NDV, NDPVS)

Vigilante groups (Bakassi Boys)

Intra and/or inter-community conflicts over rights to oil-bearing lands

Youth group violence over access to local oil rents and by providing protection services for the oil companies (Nembe)

Violent chieftaincy struggles (Okrika)

State violence and abuses by security forces (Odi, Odiana, Ogoni)

Urban violence/electoral and ward and LGA determination (Warri)

Struggles over oil-bunkering territories (Cawthorne Channel)

Inter-ethnic territorial conflicts (Ogoni-Andoni)

Cult-Fraternity groups (Icelanders, Bush Boys, and Greenlanders)

Insurgent groups (MEND)

Organised crime and violent accumulation (kidnapping as business, piracy)

For instance, a UN report in 2007 estimated that there were more than 150 conflicts across the Delta reflecting the fact that by 2005 there was a dizzying and bewildering array of militants groups, militias and cults 8and over fifty operating military camps were dotted around the creeks. In any one location a number of these conflicts may co-exist and operate in complex constellations. In Okrika for example, the conflicts encompass youth groups contesting land rights pertaining to a refinery, longstanding chieftaincy disputes (complicated by struggles over oil rents), the intrusion of cult groups, political party thuggery over local government, and vigilante groups providing community security.

Many of these groups contained a variety of ideologies and more or less explicit ideological and political positions even if many operated under the politics of ‘Resource Control’. Some groups had strong ethnic affiliations, others claimed to have Pan-Ethnic aspirations, while others represent important fault lines within ethnic minorities along the lines of age, class, clan and lineage. They were often local and territorial addressing complex configurations of larger issues of Self-Determination and Federal Principle but also local community grievances (over MOUs, spillage, access to local rents, land tenure). The mere number and proliferation of groups and conflicts speaks powerfully to the existence of a growing sense of fragmented

⁸The Niger Delta Militant Force Squad (NDMFS), the Niger Delta Strike Force (NDSF), the Grand Alliance, Niger Delta Coastal Guerillas (NDCG), South-South Liberation Movement (SSLM), Movement for the Sovereign State of the Niger Delta (MSSND), the Meinbutus, the November 1895 Movement, ELIMOTU, the Arobo Freedom Fighters, Iduwini Volunteer Force (IVF), the Niger Delta People’s Salvation Front (NDPSF), the Coalition for Militant Action (COMA), the Greenlanders, Deebam, Bush Boys, KKK, Black Braziers, Icelanders and a raft of other so-called cults.

sovereignty and of the existence of what we call “ungovernable spaces”(Joab-Peterside, Porter and Watts, 2012).

Several key points can be made about these conflicts. First, the key role - often triggering violence - of often corrupt and undisciplined military forces instigating or compounding local crises, and more profoundly of pushing political groups toward armed militancy. Second, the ways in which since 1999 electoral politics and the proliferation of local revenue flows (through increased derivation) has deepened and intensified the ferocious struggles over access to rents and what is often seen as “their resource” or “our oil”. Third, the State and the Political Classes have a history of directly supporting and sponsoring forms of violence and the circulation of arms (the electoral cycle is especially pertinent here as was obvious in 2003 and 2007). Finally, conflicts point directly to the ways in which differing forms of authority, territoriality and identity are drawn together in and around the central political logic of struggles over access to and control over oil revenues among differing forms of elite pacts and coalitions.

The Cost of Insecurity

Agitations for “Resource Control” and home rule deriving from alleged alienation of access to oil related revenue and environmental degradation resulted in emergence of ethnic militias that attack oil and gas infrastructure⁹ first, to draw attention to development deficits of the oil rich region, and later as means to generate revenue to fund insurgencies. The situation degenerated to a point where Nigeria’s export dwindled to as low as 800, 000 barrels per day compared to a targeted 2.2 million barrel for the first quarter of 2009. In 2008 alone, it was estimated that Nigeria lost over 3 trillion Naira as a result of militancy (Joab-Peterside, 2012). The unrest has turned into a criminal movement that feeds on massive theft of crude oil.

While unrest in the Delta has sharply declined since the 2009 Amnesty Deal, there was the incredible growth of oil theft and illegal refining of petroleum products in the region in spite of the clamp down on the illicit trade by State Security Forces. It was estimated that some 150,000 barrels of oil are stolen from facilities every day. The United Nations (UN) estimated that in the same year thieves stole around 150,000 barrels of oil a day. By mid-2012, the Nigerian government estimated as many as 400,000 barrels were being stolen each day costing the nation up to \$1 billion per month in lost revenues (Attah, 2012). Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) estimates its own share of the loss to be within the region of 150,000 to 180, 000 barrels per day representing about 45 per cent of the losses of the entire industry (Sunmonu, 2012).

The seeming resumption of vandalization of petroleum assets in the Niger Delta in 2016 reverberated the challenges of economic and sustainable development with particular concerns for the environment and the revenue profile of government. For example, Nigeria’s continental ranking in crude production dropped in the months of April and May 2016 for the third time in five months. Consequently, for the third time in five months, Angola beat Nigeria from the once

⁹ In March 2003, Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC), Nigeria’s biggest oil producer evacuated nonessential staff from its facilities in the Warri area due to mounting militant unrest. Shortly after SPDC, Chevron Texaco and TFE shut in (or closed) production. In combination, the shut-in of the three operations caused a supply disruption of over 800,000 barrels of oil per day, or 40 per cent of Nigeria’s national production of over 2 million barrels per day (Cesarz; Morrison and Cooke, 2003). Citing insecurity officials of unions operating in the all too often called out workers to protest insecure work environment.

undisputed largest producer in Africa. Data from the April Market Report of the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) indicated that Nigeria produced 1.677 million barrels per day in March, down from 1.744 million bpd in February while Angola oil output rose from 1.767 million to 1.782 million for the same period. The May report shows that Nigeria's production further dipped to 14 million bpd. A major factor implicated in this decline is the huge loss in production due to endemic challenge of pipeline vandalism (Onunwa, 2016).

Oil theft was exacerbated by maritime insecurity especially the inability of the Nigerian Navy to curtail the menace of sea piracy that for long time threatened the economies of member countries of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS); the Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS); and the Gulf of Guinea Commission (GGC). In fact, many vessels were attacked while at anchor, drifting, or conducting ship-to-ship transfers of refined cargo. While the activities of pirates were reduced in Somalia as a result of international patrol teams on the coast of Somalia, it increased on the West Coast because of the peculiarities of the Nigerian economy and corruption. The Local communities were also targets of sea piracy as flying boats and local traders and business men and women were victims. Some were murdered while others were maimed. The local economies were affected as local traders were afraid to ply the sea routes. Rivers and Bayelsa States were the worst hit.

Innocent people have been killed¹⁰; many were injured while properties were destroyed due to cult wars. It is highly probable that the prevailing economic situation is breeding so much discontent and criminality on the part of so many unemployed youngsters with many prone to violence. Kidnapping had done a colossal damage on Nigeria's image in the comity of nations. Tourism presently known to be among the top-three foreign earners in the globe but kidnapping has negatively affected the country's bid to develop a viable tourism industry as visitors are regularly warned by their countries to be wary of coming to the region in particular and Nigeria in general. Many would be investors have also stayed away for fears of being kidnapped.

Rivers state had faced one of Nigeria's fiercest crisis pitting Governor Simialaye Fubara against his predecessor Federal Capital Territory Minister, Nyesom Wike. Once allies, their fall out over control of State Structures and Resources spit the House of Assembly, sparking impeachment moves, protests and violence, including the burning of the House of Assembly complex. President Tinibu intervened with a peace deal, which failed to calm frayed nerves, before the declaration of emergency rule. As tempers flared, locals and ex-agitators threatened to destroy oil installations, should Governor Fubara be impeached, as threatened by pro-Wike Martin Amaewhule-led State House of Assembly through a notice to the Governor. A day before President Tinibu imposed emergency rule, an explosion rocked a section of the Trans Niger Delta Pipeline in Bodo community of Gokana Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The following day, another explosion severed a pipeline manifold in the Omwariwa axis of Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State (Abati, 2025).

The President in a statement dated Tuesday 18th March, 2025 stated thus:

Fellow Nigerians I feel greatly disturbed at the turn we have come to regarding the political crisis in Rivers State. Like many of you, I have watched with concern the development with the hope that the parties involved would allow good sense to prevail at the soonest, but all that hope

¹⁰ The latest incidence was the gruesome murder of 15 innocent people in Omuku and its surrounding communities in February 2016 and the killing of some people in the Ogoni axis of the state in June 2017.

burned out without any solution with the crisis persisting, there is no way democratic governance, which we all have fought and worked for over the years, can thrive in a way that will redound to the benefit of the good people of the State not being able to have access to the dividends of democracy.

Also, it is public knowledge that the Governor of Rivers State for unjustifiable reasons, demolished the House of Assembly of the state as far back as 13th December 2023 and has, until now, fourteen (14) months after, not rebuilt same. I have made personal interventions between the contending parties for a peaceful resolution of the crisis. I am also aware that many well-meaning Nigerians, leaders of thought and patriotic groups have also intervened at various times with the best of intentions to resolve the matter, but all their efforts were also to no avail. Still I thank them. (Ndujihe et al, 2025).

On February 28, 2025, the Supreme Court, in a judgement in respect of eight consolidated appeals concerning the political crisis in Rivers State based on several grave unconstitutional acts and disregard of rule of law that have been committed by the Governor of Rivers State as shown by evidence before it pronounced in very strong terms thus:

A government cannot be said to exist without one of the three arms that make up the government of a state under the 1999 constitution as amended. In this case the head of the Executive arm of the government has chosen to collapse the legislature to enable him govern without the legislature to enable him govern without the legislature as a despot. As it is there is no government in Rivers State”.

The above pronouncement came after a catalogue of judicial findings of constitutional breaches against the Governor Siminialyi Fubara. Going forward, in their judgement, and having found and held that 27 members of the House of Assembly who had allegedly defected” are still valid members of Rivers State House of Assembly and cannot be prevented cannot be prevented from participating in the proceeding of that House by the 8th Respondents (that is, the Governor)in cohorts by the 8th Respondents(that is, the Governor) in cohorts with four members”(Ndujihe, et al, 2025).

The Supreme Court then made some orders to restore the state to immediate constitutional democracy. These orders include the immediate passing of an Appropriation Bill by the Rivers State House of Assembly which up till now has not been facilitated. Some militants had threatened fire and brimstone against perceived enemy of the governor who has until now not disowned them. Apart from both House and the Governor who has until now has bot been able to work together for the peace and good governance of the State.

In a statement on the cessation of the emergency rule the presidency, the President said “the Governor, His Excellency Siminialayi Fubara, the Deputy Governor, Her Excellency Ngozi Odu, and members of the Rivers State House of Assembly and the Speaker, Martins Amaewhule, will resume work in their offices from September 18, 2025.

State Management of Security Challenges in the Niger Delta

The political leadership at various points in time had implemented policies to manage the incidence of violence in the belief that peace is necessary for development, few examples of these policies will suffice:

The deployment of special security forces (Joint Task force)

Establishment of Development intervention agencies/Ministries, Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC), Ministry of Niger Delta Affairs

Appointment of Special Security Committees, such as the Special Security Committee on oil Producing Areas headed by then Lt. Gen. Alexander O. Ogomudia, the Presidential Panel on National Security 2003, and the Presidential Council on the Social and Economic Development of the Coastal States of the Niger Delta (2006) to among others review the general security situation in the Region and make recommendations aimed at addressing the situation.

Declaration of Amnesty to repentant militants in the Niger Delta and implementation of Nigerian version of Disarmament, Demobilization and Reintegration (DDR) of ex-militants. The emergence of a new militant group that styled itself the Niger Delta Avengers (NDA) and its subsequent return to the trenches where they blew up some oil installations, electricity, gas and crude pipeline was a clear demonstration of the limitation of the Amnesty programme.

Award of surveillance contracts to ex-militant leaders for protection of oil pipelines in selected Niger Delta states.

The Federal Government constituted Special Anti-kidnapping squads and more funds channelled to these agencies to enhance their operations while requisite organs of some states in the Niger Delta enacted laws to stem the tide. For example, governments of Akwa Ibom, Delta and Rivers State proposed laws to enforce stiffer and strict penalties on those found guilty of the crime. For instance, Akwa Ibom and Rivers State proposed death penalty on kidnappers operating in these states. But the crime continued unabated.

Government-led Development Initiatives

Enormous resources were deployed annually by government and non-state actors to reverse the development gap in the Niger Delta. Some of these efforts were traced to the commencement of oil exportation from Oloibiri, in Rivers State. The Federal Government established various agencies to drive and coordinate its development programmes in the region. It established the Niger Delta Development Board (NDDDB) in 1960 'to manage the developmental needs' of the region'. Following the 3-year civil war which is widely believed as a struggle for control of the oil rent between the federal government and south-east regional government, the NDDDB ceased to exist, and a Presidential Task force was created by the short-lived civilian administration of former President Shehu Shagari (1979-1983). The Task Force received 1.5% of Federation Account to 'tackle the developmental problems of the region'.

The military government established the Oil Minerals Producing Area Development Commission (OMPADEC) in 1992 with 3% of the Federation Account allocated 'towards the developmental needs of the Region'. Despite the modest contributions to worsening development challenges in the Region¹¹, it suffered from lack of focus, inadequate and irregular funding, official profligacy, corruption, excessive political interference, lack of

¹¹ The Niger Delta region suffered from massive despoliation that was designed and sustained by complex conspiracy between military dictators and civilian allies, oil companies and local and international influence peddlers. Given its complicity in the crisis, the act of setting up several agencies and institutions purportedly to respond to developmental needs of the region was a mere smokescreen which at best served to extend privileged oil rent to emerging critical political voice in the region, rather than the oppressed voice of the various movements of nationalities and ethnic groups.

accountability and high overhead expenditures. It was replaced through a 2000 Bill establishing the Niger Delta Development Commission.

The NDDC was established 'to offer a lasting solution to the socio-economic difficulties of the Niger Delta and facilitate the rapid, even and sustainable development of the Niger Delta into a Region that is economically prosperous, socially stable, ecologically regenerative and politically peaceful'. The enabling Act envisaged and provided generous funding sources for the NDDC and established a Governing Board of twenty members; 10 of which are appointed by the Federal Government; 1 representative of each of the nine oil producing states and 1 representative of the oil companies operating in the region.

The NDDC Act provided the following revenue sources/contributions:

The Federal Government contributions- 15% of the monthly statutory allocations due to the nine member states of the Commission¹²

3% of Annual Budget of all oil and gas processing companies¹³

50% of the Ecological Fund Allocations due to member states;

Proceeds from NDDC Assets and miscellaneous sources, including grants, gifts, loans and donations

Like previous bodies established by the Federal government to coordinate its response in the Region, the lack of transparency and strong oversight/regulator, excessive overhead, excessive political interferences, corruption and absence of due process dog operations of NDDC. Although the Commission complains it is fund-starved by the federal government, opinions suggest that NDDC-funded projects are more expensive than any other place leading to wastage. There are suggestions that the holding back of allocations from the Commission is to allow government decide on what to do with the amorphous agency which has become another drain on national resource.

In addition to Federal government initiatives, State and Local Government Councils have mandate to steer development in their state and local government councils respectively. Current fiscal arrangement allocates 24% and 20% of balances in the federation account to state government joint account and local government joint account for this purpose. However government-led initiatives suffer coordination challenges which have been identified to promote corruption and diversion of development funds. In the absence of enabling legislation guaranteeing access to information, government activities and projects are shrouded in secrecy and it is common practice for different agencies - LG Councils, State, Federal government (NDDC) to claim ownership of the same project.

On the issue of conflict prevention, management and resolution, government have taken actions by appointing commissions and investigation panels to investigate and recommend solutions to the security challenges. Most panels of inquiry, whether judicial or administrative, usually execute their business with the seriousness it deserves. Their reports in most cases are rich in historical and empirical information, critical in analysis and blunt in recommendations.

¹² Abia, Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Imo, Ondo and Rivers States

¹³ This provision ties revenue contribution of oil companies to the NDDC to the volume of operations in the region.

If most of their recommendations were implemented, they would have gone a long way in reducing and even tackling the problems they were established to address. A case in point is the Report of the Ledum Mitee led Technical Committee on the Niger Delta (RTCND) unfortunately, government did not give the reports and recommendations the serious attention they deserve for the following reasons:

Panels in most cases, are set up to rationalize and justify government policies.

Panels are in most cases established to immediately cool down tempers, sometimes, it would seem, with no intention of implementing their recommendations.

Government in most cases do not want to tamper with the status-quo.

As a consequence of the above, the level of insecurity of both life and property in the Niger Delta accentuates on a daily basis. Within this context, stakeholders harped on proper policing of the area. Policing is an all embracing concept, involving the specific individual self-monitoring of moderation of conduct of others in context of the larger group or society. It also refers to the general or institutional level. Policing includes, but not restricted to the existence of a formal organizational facility employed in the maintenance of law, order and good governance (Wushishi, 2002).

To police conflict literary is to watch over the conditions that may result in conflict with a view to preventing them or resolving those conflicts that are in progress or those that have already occurred.

Community policing is built on community needs assessment and problem-solving. Information gathering and analysis allow police draw conclusions and make recommendations on how to solve the problems most critical to the community. The objective of community policing is to act on a proactive basis as a preventive force to deter commission of crime. To prevent undesirable behaviour through its presence, verbal interaction with the public, to interfere in incidences, produce reports and pictures for analysis and filing, and engage in rapid response deployment.

One of the novel creations of the community quest for police services is the Police-Community Relations – a standing committee of neighbourhood residents who meet with police authorities from time to time with a view to addressing their security needs in order to save their counterparts.

The vigilante mentality is also a new community response to conflict management, crime prevention and control must be carefully appraised in the light of Nigeria's contemporary political history. Some people perceive it as one of the dividends of our nascent democracy and the agitation for state police. Others consider vigilantism as employing a dangerous means to combat problems. Studies have shown that the proponents of vigilante system of policing did not contemplate the deep hatred, violence and fear that vigilantism breeds in the neighbourhood (Wushishi, 2002). Vigilante groups often times lose sight of their original functions and become increasingly corrupt, violating peoples' rights with reckless abandon.

Non-State Interventions in The Niger Delta

Development agencies throw enormous resources at the crisis in the region through direct technical and capacity assistance and NGO grants. The World Bank Group¹⁴, European Union¹⁵, UNDP, USAID¹⁶ and the Africa Development Bank provided some of the largest support to alleviate poverty.

The Food and Agriculture Organisation of the UN implemented a major national Special Programme for Food Security (SPFS). Similar project exists to improve livelihood and influence policies in favour of natural resources dependent communities. An emerging partnership trend is noticed in the number of international NGOs and foundations receiving funds from oil companies to implement community development projects as part of their social responsibility in the region¹⁷. One obvious challenge facing non-state interventions in the region is poor coordination. Interaction and information sharing is minimal among the groups.

Conclusion

The level of insecurity of both life and property in the Region is unprecedented and avoidable. It is unprecedented because it is assuming an alarming dimension, and avoidable because practical steps can be taken to check the upsurge of the negative implications of this trend. At this juncture let me briefly sketch the way forward. The 1999 constitution should be reviewed in such a way as to re-engineer the building blocks of Nigerian Federalism by addressing process issues in the practice of federalism. This is a major concern for the ethnic minorities in the Niger Delta who have called for restructuring the Nigerian Federation to ensure a more balanced and less centralized federation. This can be achieved by giving more powers and functions to the states, with the corresponding entrenched revenue empowerment otherwise known as fiscal federalism.

There is the urgent need for government at all levels to address the expectations of the citizenry for what is euphemistically referred to as the “dividends of democracy” or “stomach infrastructure”. There is a serious and understandable dent in the credibility of government score, reflecting a resolution of rising expectation after prolonged years of military rule, which seems to throw up in the long run fundamental security challenges, grindingly rising poverty, worsening living conditions, the scourge of illiteracy and disease, and decaying social and physical infrastructures, exacerbated and compounded by declining social sector investment stand in stark contrast to the opulence of the minority governing elite. Majority of citizens have lost faith and confidence in the Nigerian State and in the governing elites, seeking refuge in the informal sector or reinventing their own coping mechanisms, away from societal acceptable

¹⁴ The World Bank in 2005 signed a \$82.2 million dollar project (loan and aid) to support infrastructure, livelihood development and Natural Resource Management, Poverty Reduction in the Delta.

¹⁵ The EU implemented a €63 million grant to support rural road development, water transport, improvement and provision of health facilities, education and income generation capacity of rural persons. The programme targets the grassroots as primary beneficiaries.

¹⁶ It signed a \$20 million partnership with Shell to support cassava enterprise development; and a \$23.1 million root tubers expansion project to enhance national food-sufficiency, improve rural food security and income of farmers in Niger Delta. The project includes micro-credit enterprise, building linkages with private sector, youth development, HIV/AIDS, media and institutional support for the Judiciary.

¹⁷ Africare, an international NGO currently runs an AID project targeted at AID-orphans and Malaria roll-back project to combat malaria in rural communities

norms, and the state developmental policies which are perceived as anti-people. There is also the absence of public weal or sense of civic responsibility to ensure accountability in administration of public institutions to serve as a countervailing power against corrupt and unethical behaviour by the governing elites.

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